

Hepatoprotective Potential and Antioxidant activities of *Ricinus communis* against Paracetamol Induced Liver Damage

Loveneet Kumar^{1,2*}, Najam Ali Khan^{2,3}, Neha Saxena¹, Amit Kumar²

¹Department of Pharmacology, Umapati Mahadev College of Pharmacy, Amroha 244221 UP, India

²School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, IFTM University, Moradabad 244102 UP, India

³GMS College of Pharmacy, ShakarpurRajabpur, Amroha 244236 UP, India

Keywords

Ricinus communis; preliminary photochemical screening; hepatoprotective activity; antioxidant activity

Article History

Received January 12, 2022

Revised February 4, 2022

Accepted March 3, 2022

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine the hepatoprotective potential of an ethanolic extract of *Ricinus communis* root (EERC). On rats, the hepatoprotective potential of EERC was evaluated at dosages of 200 and 400 mg/kg (p.o.). The extracts and silymarin-treated animal groups significantly reduced the activities of various biochemical parameters, such as Serum Glutamic Oxaloacetic Transaminase (SGOT), Serum Glutamate Pyruvate Transaminase (SGPT), and Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP), which were elevated by Paracetamol intoxication. Total bilirubin, bilirubin direct, bilirubin indirect, total protein, albumin, and serum globulin levels were also normalized with EERC and silymarin. A dose of 200 mg/kg produced better results than a dose of 400 mg/kg. Treatment with EERC at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg, p.o. was found to be beneficial in repairing paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity in rats, according to histological examinations. The antioxidant potential of *R. communis* root was examined and evaluated using DPPH and H₂O₂ assays.

Graphical Abstract

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INTRODUCTION

The liver is an essential organ that regulates critical biochemical and physiological functions such as homeostasis, growth, energy and nutrient supply, drug and other xenobiotic detoxification, and infection control. As a result, it is extremely vulnerable to hepatotoxic chemicals (Mahmood et al., 2014). Hepatotoxic substances harm liver cells by causing lipid peroxidation and other oxidative liver damage. As a result, liver damage caused by hepatotoxic substances has serious consequences. As a result, toxic drugs such as CCl₄, Paracetamol, D-galactosamine, alcohol, rifampicin, and thioacetamide have a significant impact on the liver via multiple pathways, while additional agents that cause hepatotoxicity include statins, isoniazid, and numerous anti-microbial medicines (Naveen et al., 2016). Toxic liver injury can mimic almost any known pattern of injury, including necrosis, stenosis, fibrosis, cholestasis, and vascular damage. Liver damage caused by cancer treatment may not necessarily be due to hepatotoxic anticancer agents; the clinician must also examine reactions to antibiotics, analgesics, antiemetic, or other therapies. Preexisting medical conditions, tumors, immunosuppression, hepatitis viruses and other infections, nutritional deficits or total parenteral nutrition can all increase a person's susceptibility to liver injury. As a result, attributing liver damage to a toxic reaction is challenging (King et al.,

2001). Acute or chronic hepatitis (inflammatory liver illnesses), hepatosis (non-inflammatory disorders), and cirrhosis are the three types of liver diseases (degenerative disorder resulting in fibrosis of the liver). Free radicals cause cell damage by covalent binding and lipid peroxidation, resulting in tissue destruction. Natural antioxidant agents have piqued the interest of researchers because they can protect the human body from free radicals (Sreejith et al., 2014). Hepatocyte necrosis and increased levels of biochemical markers such as SGOT, SGPT, ALP, and total bilirubin levels are invariably associated with liver injury or failure. Each year, the death rate from hepatic illnesses rises. According to the FDA, drug-induced liver damage is the major cause of acute liver failure (Nallamilli et al., 2013). The severity of the symptoms varies according to the degree of exposure and thus the extent of the liver damage or injury. In which the liver is a metabolically active organ responsible for xenobiotic biotransformation and removal from the body. It is a common target for medications and microorganisms that can cause liver cell damage and impair overall function. The general method for preventing liver damage comprises lowering reactive metabolites through the use of antioxidants. Natural polyphenolic substances with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory characteristics, such as resveratrol, quercetin, curcumin, and silymarin, have been the subject of much research as liver protectants. The

treatment of drug-induced hepatotoxicity is primarily supportive, with the first step being the withdrawal of the offending substance (Rathee et al., 2017).

Liver illnesses are a widespread concern, and standard medications used to treat them are sometimes ineffective and can have dangerous side effects. As a result, there is increased interest in medicinal plants as potential sources of hepatoprotective compounds. For liver problems, a variety of plant-based traditional remedies or formulations comprising herbal extracts are available on the market (Kamisanet al., 2013). Phytonutrients, coumarins, lignans, essential oils, monoterpenes, carotenoids, glycosides, flavonoids, organic acids, lipids, alkaloids, and xanthines are among the chemical elements found in hepatoprotective herbal medications. A variety of plant extracts are also utilised to treat liver diseases. Approximately 25 plants have been identified to be useful in the treatment of liver problems (Eesha et al., 2011). *Ricinus communis* Linn. (Euphorbiaceae), also known as Eranda in Ayurveda, is a soft-wooded little tree found across the world's tropics and warm temperate regions. The leaf, root, and seed oil of this plant have been utilised in Indian medicine to treat inflammation and liver diseases. Because of the strong demand for this plant's roots, they were taken from anywhere, which is why a comparative phytochemical study was

conducted. This plant root's varieties were collected from contaminated, nonpolluted, and residential locations. As a result, phytochemical assessments and heavy metal detection were carried out to assure the purity of all types (Dhimanet al., 2016). Based on the literature review, it was determined that there is no scientific report on *Ricinus communis*'s Hepatoprotective activity in animals. As a result, we chose to test *Ricinus communis*' hepatoprotective and antioxidant capabilities against paracetamol-induced damage.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Chemicals and Instrumentation

All solvents, chemicals, solutions and reagents used in the study were of analytical grade and procured from SD Fine Chemicals and Albert David Ltd, India. Paracetamol was obtained from Ranbaxy Laboratories Ltd, New Delhi; and silymarin from Sigma Chemicals, USA. All biochemical estimation kits were obtained from Span Diagnostics Ltd., Surat; Merck Specialties Ltd., Mumbai; and Accurex Biochemical Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. Major instruments used for the study were ultraviolet spectrophotometer (PharmaSpec UV-1700 Shimadzu) and centrifuge machine (Mini centrifuge, Spinnwell)

Identification, Collection, and Authentication of Plant Material

Ricinuss communis Linn plant was collected in the month of May-2017 from the botanical garden of IFTM University, Moradabad, India. Authentication of the plant was done by the botanist, Department of Botany, IFTM University, Moradabad, India (Voucher specimen No 2017/SOS/BOT/53ss).

Preparation of Root extract

R. communis root was dried at room temperature, and the dried roots were ground into a coarse powder and passed through sieve No. 18. To remove fatty content and other pigments, powdered leaves were defatted using petroleum ether (40-60%). Using Soxhlet apparatus, the defatted dry leaves were extracted with ethanol. In a vacuum oven, the extracts were concentrated to dryness until all traces of ethanol were eliminated. After standing heating in a boiling water bath for about 80 minutes with recurrent agitation, the extracts were stored in a refrigerator at a temperature of 2-8°C for further use (Bukhari et al., 2012).

Preliminary Phytochemical Tests

The extract obtained from different solvents was subjected to various chemical tests for the determination of phytoconstituents presents in them (Khandelwal, 2005; Pandey et al., 2014)

Animals

Healthy adult (either sex) Wistar rats (250-300 gram) were obtained from the animal house of

IFTM University. The animals (n=6) were housed in polypropylene cages at a temperature (28± 2°C) with RH (60-70%) and 12:12 h dark/light cycle. The animals had free access to standard pellet chow during the study protocol. The animal had free access to water. The pharmacology and acute toxicity protocols were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee, IFTM University, Moradabad with reference no. CPCSEA (2017/837ac/MPh/03).

Standardization of the Dose by Acute Oral Toxicity Study

The acute Hepatotoxicity was performed according to the OPPTS (Office and Prevention, Pesticides and Toxic Substance) Guideline following up and down procedure.

In-Vivo Evaluation

Hepatoprotective Activity

The *in vivo* hepatoprotective activity of EERC was determined using the PCM-induced hepatotoxicity test in rats. The animals (n = 6) were randomly divided into 5 experimental groups and administered with test solutions as follows.

- Group I served as normal control (Tween 80 10%).
- Group II served as toxic control (Paracetamol 2000 mg/kg).
- Group III served as standard group (Silymarin).

Pretreatment groups:

- Group IV group treated with low dose (200 mg/kg p.o.) of alcoholic extract of RC.
- Group V group treated with high dose (400 mg/kg p.o.) of alcoholic extract of RC.

The current investigation used low dosages of EERC (mg/kg) extract based on a prior report on an acute toxicity trial utilizing large doses of EERC (mg/kg) supplied orally, which showed no symptoms of toxicity in rats. The animals were fasted for 48 hours before to the experiment under regular laboratory circumstances, but were given unlimited access to water. After 48 hours, each group was given the appropriate dose of test solution orally once day for 7 days. Except for group I, PCM was administered orally three hours after the final extract administration on the seventh day. After 48 hours of hepatic damage induction, animals were mildly sedated with diethyl ether and blood was taken via heart puncture in sterilized centrifugation tubes, which were subsequently centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to obtain serum for biochemical parameters analysis. After that, the animals were sacrificed by cervical dislocation, and the liver was taken for histopathological investigations (Eesha et al., 2011).

***In-vitro* Antioxidant Study**

DPPH (2, 2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl)

The DPPH test is widely used in natural product antioxidant research. One of the reasons for this is that the procedure is straightforward and sensitive. The hypothesis behind this assay is that a hydrogen donor is an antioxidant. It assesses chemicals that act as radical scavengers. The method by which DPPH takes hydrogen from an antioxidant is seen in the figure below. DPPH is one of the few organic nitrogen radicals that is both stable and commercially available (MacDonald-Wicks et al., 2006; Lewis, 2012). The antioxidant effect is proportional to the amount of DPPH that is removed from test samples. Because of its ease and precision, monitoring DPPH with a UV spectrometer has become the most often used method. At 517 nm, DPPH has a significant absorption maximum (purple). When hydrogen from an antioxidant is absorbed, the color changes from purple to yellow, followed by the production of DPPH. In terms of the number of hydrogen atoms absorbed, this process is stoichiometric. As a result, the antioxidant impact can be easily assessed by monitoring the decrease in UV absorption at 517 nm.

Preparation of test Solution

To prepare a stock solution of 1 mg/ml, 100 mg of dried ethanolic extract was diluted in 100 ml of ethanol. Aliquots of this solution were further diluted with ethanol to the

necessary concentration.

Preparation of DPPH (0.1mM)

In 10 mL of ethanol, 39.43 mg DPPH was dissolved. 1 mL of this solution was taken and diluted with ethanol up to 10 ml. Then, take 5ml of this created solution and dilute it with ethanol to make a total volume of 50ml.

Procedure

2 ml solution of DPPH (0.1 mms) solution was added to 2 ml of various concentrations of extract. As a control, an equal amount of ethanol and DPPH was used. The absorbance was measured at 517 nm after 30 minutes of incubation in the dark. The experiment was carried out three times. The formula was used to compute the percentage of scavenging (Sachan et al., 2016).

Hydrogen Peroxide Scavenging Capacity

The ability of the *R. communis* extract to scavenge hydrogen peroxide was assessed using Ruch et al., 1989's technique. In phosphate buffer, a 40mM solution of hydrogen peroxide was produced (pH 7.4). A distilled water extract (100 g/mL) was mixed with a hydrogen peroxide solution (0.6 mL). Ten minutes later, the absorbance of hydrogen peroxide at 230 nm was measured in comparison to a blank solution containing the phosphate buffer but no hydrogen peroxide. The hydrogen peroxide scavenging percentage

of *R. communis* extracts and reference compounds was determined.

$$\begin{aligned} \% \text{ Scavenged } [H2O2] \\ = [(AC - AS)/AC] \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

Where AC is the absorbance of the control and AS is the absorbance in the presence of the sample of *R. communis* extract.

Histopathological Study

From each group, a piece of the liver was fixed in 10% formasal (formalin diluted to 10% with saline), cleaned with xylene, and safeguarded for histology. For histopathology, 5-6 mm thick slices were stained with hematoxylin and eosin dye for microscopic examination of histological abnormalities in the liver. Following that, the liver sections were scored and graded based on the severity of the hepatic injury, as previously reported with minor alterations. Evaluation of hepatoprotective activity. Serum glutamate pyruvate transaminase (SGPT) and serum glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase (SGOT) activity were measured using the Reitman and Frankel method. To assess the damage produced by Paracetamol, the activities of alkaline phosphatase (ALP), acid phosphatase (ACP), total ATPases, protein and glycogen content, lipid peroxide, and glutathione level were all estimated in liver tissue (Princea et al., 2011).

RESULTS

Preliminary Phytochemical Studies

Several phytochemical assays were performed on an ethanolic extract of *R. communis* Root. The presence of alkaloids, glycosides, protein, tannins & phenolic compounds, flavonoids, amino acids, and fats & oils was revealed in preliminary phytochemical screening of EERC Root. The results obtained were presented in table 1.

Acute Toxicity Study

The EERC root was tested for acute toxicity at a dose of 2000 mg/kg in this study. In treated animals, there was no evidence of toxicity from the extracts. As a result, 200 and 400 mg/kg were chosen for further research.

Hepatoprotective Evaluation

Effects of EERC Root on Serum Marker Enzymes SGOT, SGPT, and ALP

The biochemical characteristics of the mice revealed that low doses of EERC had a considerable reduction. The raised levels of SGOT and SGPT, as well as the high dose of EERC, reveal both non-significant ant ion have parameters. However, the high dose of EERC also considerably reduced the elevated level of ALP. Low doses of EERC likewise greatly reduced the increased, however high doses of EERC were ineffective. The percentage protection provided by silymarin against increases in SGOT, SGPT, and ALP levels was 50.33, 65.55, and 133.33, respectively.

Effect of EERC on Total bilirubin, Bilirubin direct, Bilirubin indirect, serum Total Protein, Serum Albumin, and Globulin, in PCM induced Hepatotoxicity.

It was found that there was a considerable increase in serum bilirubin and protein levels in the group following PCM intoxication, which was prevented by EERC and indicated a drop in levels. Pretreatment with silymarin and EERC greatly inhibited the biochemical alterations generated by PCM as compared to PCM intoxication. The hepatoprotective effect of EERC 200 mg/kg was found to be larger than that of EERC 400 mg/kg.

***In-vitro* antioxidant activity**

The antioxidant activity was determined using the DPPH and H₂O₂ assays. On the basis of the research, we selected ascorbic acid (vitamin C) as a reference, which is renowned for its ability to scavenge H₂O₂ and DPPH. We have now measured the potency of ascorbic acid and EERC at various doses (10-50 g/mL). The sample was incubated for 30 minutes to finish the reaction point with the scavenger molecule, and the difference in scavenging activity between different doses of ascorbic acid with respect to EERC indicated excellent findings. In which the EERC was used as a test to observe scavenging in relation to a standard medication. Furthermore, our results demonstrated that as EERC concentrations grew, the effect of H₂O₂ and DPPH was limited and found to be raised as

concentration by decreasing the scavenging property at 517 and 510 nm. In which the analysis of the graphical curve to signify the two concentrations (50 and 80 g/mL) in Fig. 1 was associated with DPPH assay and H₂O₂ assay scavenging property.

Histopathological observations

The hepatocyte's histological appearance reflects their conditions. Liver cells from rats given 2000 mg/kg paracetamol showed significant focal necrosis, lymphocytic infiltrate, substantial hydropic edema with rosette formation, lymphocytic exudates, and

dilated congested arteries in portal tracts. Prior to paracetamol treatment, liver cells treated with 10 mg/kg of the standard medication Silymarin exhibited improvement in histology with granular cytoplasm, slight congestion in central veins, modest portal tract infiltration, and few localized necrosis. Treatment with EERC200 mg/kg improved the histological appearance of hepatocytes in a manner similar to treatment with silymarin. Congestion in the portal tracts was less than in the silymarin group, and there was minor sinusoidal dilation and mildly enlarged cells.

Table 1: Preliminary phytochemical tests to identify the presence of various Phytochemicals in Ethanol extract of EERC Root

S.No.	Phytochemical Parameters	Result
1.	Alkaloids	+
2.	Carbohydrates	-
3.	Glycosides	+
4.	Phytosterols	+
5.	Tannins and phenolic compounds	+
6.	Flavonoids	+
7.	Protein	+
8.	Steroids	-
9.	Amino Acids	+
10.	Fats And Oils	+
(+): Presence, (-): Absence		

Table 2: Effect of administration of EERC on biochemical parameters against PCM-induced hepatotoxicity

Group	SGOT (IU/L)	SGPT (IU/L)	ALP (IU/L)
Control	40.22±0.069	81.41±0.097	123.00±0.966
PCM intoxicated (2 g/kg)	130.79±0.037	148.28±0.082	177.00±1.452
Standard (silymarin 100 mg/kg, p.o.) + PCM	50.33±0.091*	65.55±0.120*	133.33±1.201***
Low Dose (EERC 200 mg/kg) + PCM	60.58±0.098*	70.54±0.094*	148.16±3.515***
High Dose (EERC 400 mg/kg) + PCM	110.56±0.109ns	128.54±0.130ns	164.66±1.229***

All values are mean ± SEM. Statistical analysis of data was carried out by one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test. NS=non-significant, * ($p<0.05$), ** ($p<0.01$) and *** ($p<0.001$) when compared with the PCM intoxicated group.

Table 3: The effect of EERC on Total serum Bilirubin, Bilirubin Direct, Bilirubin Indirect, Total protein, serum Albumin and Globulin levels in PCM-induced hepatotoxicity in rats

Group	Total serum Bilirubin (mg/dl)	Bilirubin Direct (mg/dl)	Bilirubin Indirect (mg/dl)	Total protein (gm/dl)	Serum Albumin (gm/dl)	Globulin (gm/dl)
Control	0.96±0.0096	0.47±0.0099	0.66±0.0094	7.37±0.1113	4.65±0.1351	2.66±0.0970
PCM intoxicated (2 g/kg)	1.90±0.0106	1.13±0.0116	1.16±0.0096	8.63±0.0337	5.57±0.0990	4.24±0.0699
Standard (silymarin 100 mg/kg, p.o.) + PCM	0.76±0.0094* **	0.46±0.01137 ***	0.50±0.0125* **	6.67±0.0265* **	4.52±0.1005* **	2.58±0.1048* **
Low Dose (EERC 200 mg/kg) + PCM	0.95±0.0107* **	0.41±0.0140* **	0.34±0.0094* **	6.88±0.0515* **	4.66±0.0743* **	2.84±0.0363* **
High Dose (EERC 400 mg/kg) + PCM	1.81±0.0106* **	0.91±0.0094*	0.90±0.0124*	7.40±0.1059* **	4.85±0.0463* **	4.07±0.0272ns

All values are expressed in mean \pm SEM. Statistical analysis of data was carried out by one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test. * ($p < 0.05$), ** ($p < 0.01$) and *** ($p < 0.001$) when compared with the PCM intoxicated group.

Table 4: The antioxidant activity as percent scavenging ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) for DPPH assay of EERC

S. No	Concentration	EERC Absorbance	Ascorbic Acid
1	20	68.75	91.79
2	40	50.78	65.98
3	50	42.58	46.63
4	60	28.13	37.54
5	80	16.8	15.25

Figure 1. Scavenging effect of EERC and DPPH

Table 5: The antioxidant activity as percent scavenging ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) for H_2O_2 assay of EERC

S. No	Concentration	EERC	Ascorbic Acid
1	20	58.22	91.79
2	40	49.89	65.98
3	50	36.49	46.63
4	60	25.79	37.54
5	80	17.23	15.25

Figure 2. Scavenging effect of EERC and H₂O₂

Figure 3: Paraffin sections of liver stained by hematoxylin and eosin for histopathological changes. (a) Liver section of control group (b) treatment with PCM (c) Liver section treated with silymarin and PCM (d) Liver section treated with EERC (200 mg/kg) and PCM (e) Liver section treated with EERC (400 mg/kg) and PCM.

DISCUSSION

Paracetamol is a well-known antipyretic and analgesic that, in large dosages, causes liver necrosis. It is typically excreted primarily as sulphate and glucuronide. At hazardous levels, the sulfation and glucuronidation pathways become saturated, and greater percentages of paracetamol molecules are oxidized by cytochrome-450 enzymes to highly reactive NAPQI. Semiquinone radicals, formed by one-electron reduction of NAPQI, can covalently attach to cellular

membrane molecules, increasing lipid peroxidation and causing tissue damage. Higher dosages of paracetamol and NAPQI can alkylate and oxidize intracellular GSH, depleting the liver GSH pool and resulting in enhanced lipid peroxidation and liver injury. In the evaluation of acetaminophen-induced liver damage (Ramachandra et al., 2007; Jain et al., 2016; Ravikumar et al., 2011, Sengupta et al., 2011). The most typical method is to measure enzyme levels such as AST, ALT, ALP, and LDH. Hepatocellular

necrosis or membrane injury causes the enzymes to enter the bloodstream and can thus be detected in the serum. A high AST level implies liver disease, such as viral hepatitis, a heart attack, or muscle injury. AST catalyzes the conversion of alanine to pyruvate and glutamate and is thereafter released in the same manner. As a result, because ALT is more specific to the liver, it is a superior measure for diagnosing liver injury. Serum enzyme levels that are elevated are symptomatic of cellular leakage and a loss of functional integrity of the cell membrane in the liver. Serum levels of ALP, bilirubin, and TP, on the other hand, are linked to hepatic cell activity (Raj Kapoor et al., 2008).

At a dose of (2000 mg/kg b.w.) ethanolic extract of *R. communis* root showed no sign and symptom toxicity. Oral administration of paracetamol causes an increase in serum biochemical markers that may cause liver damage in rats. The treated group of silymarin and EERC revealed a significant decrease in the treatment's serum profile. The blood enzymes SGOT, SGPT, and ALK-Phosphate are key indicators of liver function. Paracetamol significantly increases SGOT, SGPT, ALP, Urea, Total serum Bilirubin, Bilirubin Direct, and bilirubin reduces total protein (TP), globulin, and albumin levels. The levels of these indicators were restored after administration

of the plant extract, or silymarin. The reversal could be attributed to its membrane-stabilizing activity, which prevents intracellular enzyme leakage. This is consistent with the widely held belief that serum transaminase levels revert to normal with hepatic parenchymal repair and hepatocyte regeneration (Wegner et al., 1999). The efficacy of any hepatoprotective medicine is determined by its ability to either lessen the detrimental effect of a hepatotoxin or restore normal liver function. The drug-like silymarin and the plant extract reduced increased enzyme levels in the tested groups, indicating protection of hepatocytic cell membrane structural integrity or regeneration of damaged liver cells. This mechanism may be accomplished through the antioxidant activity of EERC (Mujeeb et al., 2007). Furthermore, defense mechanisms that can occur include activation of liver regeneration by increasing protein and glycoprotein production or quicker detoxification and excretion (Kumar et al., 2004), avoidance of lipid peroxidation, and stabilization of the hepatocellular membrane. According to the microscopic examination, EERC had hepatoprotective efficacy against PCM-induced liver damage in the current investigation. The discovery is bolstered further by the normalization of histopathological changes in order to retain the histostructure of hepatocytes.

Furthermore, the EERC-induced hepatoprotective effects were nearly comparable to that of a typical hepatoprotective medication. However, the findings merit additional examination, and more in-depth research is presently underway to establish the putative hepatoprotective mechanism(s) involved, as well as to isolate and identify the responsible bioactive chemicals produced from EERC.

CONCLUSION

According to the findings of this investigation, an ethanolic extract of *R. communis* shown strong hepatoprotective effect in hepatotoxic rats. It has a hepatoprotective effect during treatment, with a considerable improvement in hepatic damage recovery. When compared to the hepatotoxic group, the serum marker enzymes SGOT, SGPT, and other parameters reveal a dramatically reduced effect. This action could be attributed to the presence of glycosides, flavonoids, alkaloids, and other substances in the leaves, which could act synergistically or independently in increasing enzyme activity. The findings imply that additional research into the potential hepatoprotective properties of *R. communis* root is required. The molecular identification of the chemical responsible for hepatoprotective effect, as well as the mechanism, are still being researched.

Acknowledgments

The authors extend their gratitude to the Hon'ble Vice Chancellor and Dean, School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, IFTM University, Moradabad.

Author's Contribution

Loveneet Kumar: Planned, experimented, and wrote the manuscript. Dr. Najam Ali: Supervised the experiment, performed major corrections in the experiment, reviewed and edited the manuscript. Neha Saxena and Amit Kumar helped in experiment work. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration

Ethical Approval All experimental procedures relating to animals were conducted as per the CPCSEA guidelines for laboratory animals. The protocol was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) of IFTM University, Moradabad, India (Approval No. CPCSEA (2017/837ac/MPh/03)).

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How to cite this article: Kumar L, Khan NA, Saxena N, Kumar A. Hepatoprotective Potential and Antioxidant activities of *Ricinus communis* against Paracetamol Induced Liver Damage. The CMP Journal of International Studies in Health and Pharmaceutical Sciences.